

**NEUROGENETIC
PROFILE,
COMMUNICATION AND
EDUCATIONAL
INTERVENTION IN
STUDENTS WITH CHD8
SYNDROME**

PERFIL NEUROGENÉTICO, COMUNICACIÓN E
INTERVENCIÓN EDUCATIVA EN EL ALUMNADO
CON SÍNDROME CHD8

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2026

ABSTRACT: CHD8 syndrome is a genetic alteration associated with Autism Spectrum Disorder, Intellectual Disability, and language difficulties, characterized by a specific neurogenetic and communicative profile with important implications in the educational field. Despite growing interest from clinical and biomedical perspectives, there are still limitations in research focused on its educational participation and intervention, especially regarding communicative and linguistic development.

The aim of this study is to analyze the neurocognitive, communicative, and behavioral profile associated with CHD8 syndrome, as well as to describe its educational implications and propose an intervention aimed at developing students' communicative skills in inclusive settings. To this end, a theoretical review of the existing literature is conducted, and pedagogical strategies are proposed that integrate the different components of language (form, content, and use), along with executive functions.

The findings highlight the need to implement comprehensive, structured, and functional educational approaches that promote students' participation and interaction in the classroom. In this regard, the importance of adapting intervention to the specific characteristics of this profile is emphasized, fostering communicative and linguistic development as a foundation for effective interaction with the environment.

Keywords: *CHD8 syndrome; Autism Spectrum Disorder; educational intervention; communication skills; inclusive settings.*

Resumen: El síndrome CHD8 es una alteración genética asociada al Trastorno del Espectro Autista, Discapacidad Intelectual y dificultades en el lenguaje, caracterizada por un perfil neurogenético y comunicativo específico con importantes implicaciones en el ámbito educativo. A pesar del creciente interés desde perspectivas clínicas y biomédicas, persisten limitaciones en la investigación centrada en su participación e intervención educativa, especialmente en relación con el desarrollo comunicativo y lingüístico.

El presente trabajo tiene como objetivo analizar el perfil neurocognitivo, comunicativo y conductual asociado al síndrome CHD8, así como describir sus implicaciones educativas y proponer una intervención didáctica orientada al desarrollo de las habilidades comunicativas del alumnado en contextos inclusivos. Para ello, se realiza una revisión teórica de la literatura existente y se plantean estrategias pedagógicas que integran los distintos componentes del lenguaje (forma, contenido y uso), junto con las funciones ejecutivas.

Los resultados evidencian la necesidad de implementar enfoques educativos integrales, estructurados y funcionales que favorezcan la participación e interacción del alumnado en el aula. En este sentido, se destaca la importancia de adaptar la intervención a las características específicas de este perfil, promoviendo el desarrollo comunicativo y lingüístico como base para una interacción eficaz con el entorno.

Palabras clave: *síndrome CHD8; Trastorno del Espectro Autista; intervención educativa; habilidades comunicativas; contextos inclusivos.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

The CHD8 gene stands out for its involvement in neurodevelopment and for its association with a specific subtype of ASD, characterized by alterations in social communication, language, and certain cognitive functions (Bernier et al., 2014; Satterstrom et al., 2020).

These manifestations suggest a direct impact on both communicative processes and access to and participation in school learning, which makes this gene a topic of significant interest from both a clinical and educational perspective. However, despite advances in genetic and neurobiological knowledge, the information available regarding its application in educational contexts remains limited.

Most studies focus on the clinical, molecular, or behavioral characterization of the CHD8 profile, while only a few investigate its pedagogical implications, the design of intervention strategies, or the development of specific teaching resources.

This lack of transfer between scientific evidence and educational practice makes it difficult to generate guidance tailored to students' real needs, especially in relation to communicative and linguistic development. Likewise, this shortage of studies applied to the school setting highlights the need to develop evidence-based educational proposals that make it possible to translate scientific findings into concrete intervention strategies.

In the case of students with CHD8 syndrome, it is especially important to identify which supports promote better understanding of the environment, more effective communication, and greater participation in classroom activities.

In this way, research progress would not only broaden knowledge about this neurogenetic profile, but also improve the educational response offered from an inclusive perspective adapted to their needs.

2. OBJECTIVES

The analysis of the neurocognitive, linguistic, and behavioral profile associated with mutations in the CHD8 gene is the central focus of this work. This section aims to provide an integrated and well-founded overview of the main characteristics that define this profile within Autism Spectrum Disorder, addressing both its neurobiological basis and its manifestation in language development, cognition, and behavior. The aim is not only to describe these characteristics, but also to interpret them from a functional perspective, that is, by considering how they influence communication, learning, and interaction in real educational contexts.

Likewise, this analysis seeks to serve as a bridge between scientific knowledge and educational practice, making it possible to translate research findings into implications relevant for intervention. In this way, it aims to identify patterns of functioning that can guide educational decision-making, especially in relation to adapting the environment, selecting teaching strategies, and supporting communicative development.

On the basis of this theoretical framework, the goal is to support an educational intervention proposal tailored to the specific needs of this profile, with particular emphasis on the development of functional and pragmatic communication in inclusive school settings.

The following specific objectives are established:

- To describe the main neurocognitive, linguistic, and behavioral characteristics associated with the CHD8 profile, based on scientific evidence.
- To analyze the educational implications, especially in relation to classroom participation and communicative development.
- To identify the specific educational needs of students with CHD8 alterations in inclusive school settings and provide practical guidelines that support the implementation of classroom strategies.
- To design a didactic intervention proposal focused on the development of functional and pragmatic communication.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK: NEUROGENETIC AND COMMUNICATIVE PROFILE

This section describes the neurogenetic, cognitive, and behavioral bases of CHD8 syndrome. It also examines the communicative and linguistic development of the students who present it, and its impact on the receptive, expressive, and pragmatic levels of language.

3.1. NEUROGENETIC BASIS OF CHD8

The CHD8 gene (Chromodomain Helicase DNA-binding protein 8) has been identified as one of the key regulators of gene expression during neuroembryonic development, located on chromosome 14, and plays an essential role in neuronal proliferation, cell migration, and cortical organization (Bernier et al., 2014). As these authors note, mutations in this gene are consistently associated with a syndromic subtype within Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), characterized by high penetrance and a relatively well-defined neurobiological profile.

From a neurocognitive perspective, several studies have reported alterations in both cortical and subcortical structures, including the neocortex, hippocampus, amygdala, and striatum. These difficulties are related to dysfunction in frontostriatal networks and cortical connectivity, which affects brain development and expression (Bernier et al., 2014; Beighley et al., 2020).

Likewise, recent research has pointed to the presence of an atypical attentional pattern, characterized by difficulties in modulating sustained and selective attention, which may hinder learning acquisition in structured educational settings.

From a medical standpoint, neuroanatomical correlates such as macrocephaly and increased brain volume in the early stages of development have also been described, suggesting alterations in growth processes, neuronal migration, and synaptogenesis or apoptosis (Bernier et al., 2014; Fidler et al., 2000). Taken together, this body of evidence reinforces the need to understand the cognitive profile of CHD8 syndrome from an integrative perspective that considers both the structural and functional aspects of neurodevelopment.

3.2. LINGUISTIC AND COMMUNICATIVE PROFILE

Language development in people with CHD8 alterations shows considerable heterogeneity, with language and speech delays of varying severity being reported (Mitchel et al., 2022).

From a speech and language therapy perspective, these difficulties appear as limitations in communicative initiation, maintaining conversational exchange, and adapting discourse to the social context.

Research in the field of language has shown that, although some individuals may develop relatively preserved formal language structures, communicative skills consistent with the clinical profile remain impaired (Bernier et al., 2014; Beighley et al., 2020). In this way, communicative development becomes a central feature of the linguistic profile, affecting skills such as inference, understanding communicative intentions, expressing linguistic forms, and using figurative language.

Likewise, studies in language neuroscience suggest that these difficulties may be related to alterations in neural networks involved in social and linguistic processing, such as the mirror neuron system and temporoparietal areas, which are also present in individuals with ASD (Redcay & Courchesne, 2008).

From a clinical speech and language perspective, authors such as Paul, Norbury, and Gosse (2018) stress the importance of intervening not only in the structural aspects of language, but also in its functionality, prioritizing natural communication contexts and strategies that support the generalization of the student's learning.

However, in the specific case of CHD8 syndrome, the lack of language-focused studies makes it necessary to extrapolate evidence from ASD, always from a critical and contextualized perspective, avoiding overgeneralizations.

3.3. BEHAVIORAL AND SOCIOEMOTIONAL PROFILE

The behavioral profile associated with CHD8 falls within the characteristic manifestations of the autism spectrum, including repetitive and stereotyped behavior patterns, a preference for environmental sameness, and persistent difficulties in emotional regulation and social interactions (Bernier et al., 2014; Beighley et al., 2020). However, some observations suggest that this subtype may present particular features in the intensity and expression of these traits, reinforcing the need for a specific analysis of this genetic alteration.

Regarding the socioemotional domain, some cases have reported difficulties in social cognition consistent with ASD patterns (An et al., 2020), especially in understanding other people's mental states, interpreting social cues, and producing emotionally appropriate responses in context. These limitations directly affect the quality of social interactions and participation in inclusive educational settings. Consequently, the literature highlights the interaction among cognitive, sensory, and emotional factors in the emergence of maladaptive behaviors, such as difficulties in understanding environmental elements and their relationships. In this way, alterations in sensory processing may contribute to avoidance responses, overload, or behavioral dysregulation (Marco et al., 2011).

In the clinical field, emphasis is placed on interventions that integrate emotional regulation strategies, environmental structuring, and explicit teaching of social skills, in order to better support the patient's adaptation to everyday demands. This type of approach makes it possible to provide more tailored support, reduce dysregulation, and promote more functional participation in different interaction contexts. Overall, the behavioral profile of CHD8 syndrome highlights the need for interdisciplinary approaches that consider the interaction among the different domains of development, fostering comprehensive and context-sensitive intervention.

4. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE CHD8 PROFILE

4.1. FROM NEUROGENETIC EVIDENCE TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE

Data gathered on CHD8 syndrome has helped delineate unique characteristics reflected in a subtype within Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) with notable implications for understanding educational needs. Despite this, educational literature continues to show a significant gap between neurobiological knowledge of the condition and its transfer to the classroom, hindering the development of evidence-based pedagogical practices (Lord et al., 2020; Leifler et al., 2021).

Current educational models emphasize that inclusion of individuals with disabilities should not be understood solely through their individual traits, but as the result of the interaction between the student's characteristics and the challenges presented by the environment (UNCRPD, 2006). This ecological paradigm demands structural and systematic adaptation of educational contexts, particularly for profiles with alterations in communication and social interaction, emotional regulation, and executive functions, to promote their social and physical well-being.

Several studies have demonstrated that effective inclusion of students with ASD largely depends on implementing structural, organizational, and methodological adjustments in the classroom, rather than interventions focused exclusively on the student (Sutton et al., 2017; Leifler et al., 2021). Within this framework, the CHD8 profile requires a highly structured, predictable, and visually organized educational design.

4.2. IMPLICATIONS FOR COMMUNICATIVE DEVELOPMENT: A FUNCTIONAL SPEECH THERAPY PERSPECTIVE

From a speech therapy standpoint, evidence consistently points to the main difficulties in ASD lying in the pragmatic domain of language—that is, the functional use of communication in real social contexts (Tager-Flusberg et al., 2005; Paul et al., 2018). In the case of CHD8 syndrome, these difficulties appear accompanied by alterations in the integration between language and executive

cognition, affecting communicative planning and discourse coherence (Friedman & Sterling, 2019).

Research on communicative intervention for students with ASD highlights the effectiveness of naturalistic and functional approaches, particularly those prioritizing intentional communication over linguistic form (Sandbank et al., 2020; Klefbeck et al., 2021). Thus, intervention should focus on developing overall communicative competence, integrating all language components: phonetic-phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic aspects.

Current reviews of alternative and augmentative communication systems (AAC) emphasize their importance for enhancing students' communicative skills and access to functional language in inclusive school settings (Paul et al., 2018; Klefbeck et al., 2021). Among the most widely used in educational contexts are systems with Augmented Natural Language (ANL), as they support communicative development by presenting linguistic models in real contexts through voice and visual supports on dynamic boards (Ronski & Sevcik, 2005; Binger & Light, 2007). In this way, dynamic communicators enable associating symbol, word, and meaning, fostering communicative skills in natural contexts (Light & McNaughton, 2012).

These strategies should not be seen as substitutes for oral language, but as tools enabling communicative exchange and social participation for those who benefit from them.

4.3. PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATIONS FOR SCHOOL INCLUSION

Regarding pedagogical implications, including students with complex neurodevelopmental profiles requires reorganizing teaching practices toward more integrative, flexible, structured, and organized models. Studies report that a student's mere presence in the regular classroom does not guarantee adapted participation, interaction, and educational inclusion, necessitating specific methodological, spatial, and material strategies to address their manifested characteristics (Booth & Ainscow, 2011; Leifler et al., 2021).

For CHD8 syndrome, limitations in executive functions, cognitive flexibility, and behavioral regulation imply the need for strategies based on visual anticipation, structuring of spaces and times, and segmentation of proposed activities. Study

results indicate that highly structured environments lead to significant improvements in student comprehension and integration with environmental elements, especially when combined with visual supports and predictable routines (Sutton et al., 2017; Friedman & Sterling, 2019).

Consequently, research in inclusive pedagogy underscores the relevance of socially mediated learning through strategies such as structured cooperative learning, peer tutoring, and explicit teacher modeling (Conn et al., 2020). These techniques not only foster student social interaction but also support communicative skill development in naturally structured contexts.

Finally, several authors highlight teacher training as a key factor in the effectiveness of educational inclusion, particularly for students requiring support due to special educational needs. Effective implementation of evidence-based strategies depends on teachers' professional competence in adapting instruction to students' characteristics in the classroom (Sutton et al., 2017; Klefbeck et al., 2021).

5. EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION PROPOSAL

This section describes the educational intervention proposal designed for students with CHD8 syndrome, whose main objective is to provide concrete and applicable tools to improve their communicative and linguistic skills in educational settings.

5.1. METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES

Methodological principles are defined as the strategies and techniques for structuring, organizing, and sequencing teaching and learning processes in the classroom to promote student participation and integration with peers.

Thus, it is essential to organize the educational environment in a clear and predictable manner, structuring space, time, and tasks to enhance understanding of classroom demands and enable anticipation of activities.

In this way, anticipation plays a fundamental role, as the use of visual supports, schedules, and structured routines allows students to foresee what will happen at each moment, fostering their participation and integration in the environment while reducing anxiety from changes. Additionally, the intervention should focus

on the functionality of learning, prioritizing communicative skills that can be used in real and meaningful contexts for the student. Therefore, explicit teaching based on modeling communicative and linguistic behaviors, with guided practice from professionals, is required to develop their abilities.

Finally, promoting the generalization of learning across various contexts is crucial to enhance engagement with peers and support physical and social well-being in communicative situations.

5.2. STRATEGIES FOR COMMUNICATIVE DEVELOPMENT

Communicative intervention must be approached from a global perspective that encompasses both functional and structural aspects of language, aiming to promote effective and satisfactory communication in natural and inclusive educational contexts.

First, developing **functional communication** is a priority, as it involves equipping students with techniques and tools to express, produce, or evoke needs, desires, and interests in real situations. To achieve this, it is necessary to create communicative opportunities where students can actively participate in the classroom, encouraging pragmatic language use for requesting, rejecting, choosing, or commenting to other interlocutors. The use of visual supports or augmentative communication systems can be particularly useful in this process, facilitating access to constructing communicative statements.

Second, **intervention in pragmatic language** should focus on the social use of language, employing student communicative skills such as respecting turns, initiating and maintaining interactions, and adapting discourse to the communicative context. These skills can be acquired through structured activities like modeling, social scripts, or dramatization of everyday situations in structured contexts.

On the other hand, **language comprehension** requires the teacher to adapt language, enabling students to understand the functioning of given instructions, the segmentation of provided information, and linguistic processing through visual supports. These techniques reduce cognitive load and improve content accessibility to the student's characteristics.

Regarding **verbal expression**, intervention should be oriented toward the progressive development of oral or alternative language through linguistic modeling strategies, syntactic expansion (structured amplification of statements produced by the student), functional repetition of new and unknown vocabulary, and positive reinforcement of articulatory approximation attempts in student productions. This approach not only enhances expressive competence but also boosts motivation for functional communication use, incorporating emotional learning components that reinforce engagement, communicative confidence, and willingness to interact.

5.3. TOOLS AND RESOURCES

Educational intervention for students with CHD8 syndrome requires the use of visual tools and materials that facilitate access to communication, understanding of the environment, and active participation in classroom dynamics. In this regard, augmentative and alternative communication systems (AAC) are a fundamental resource for promoting communicative skill development, especially for students with difficulties in oral language expression and organization. The use of dynamic communicators, visual boards, or pictogram-based systems fosters communicative intent and promotes functional and meaningful interactions (Ronski & Sevcik, 2005; Light & McNaughton, 2012).

Likewise, visual images—whether pictographic, ideographic, or composite—facilitate language representation and support comprehension of concepts, actions, and social norms within the educational context. These supports reduce linguistic load and improve verbal information processing, contributing to greater cognitive and communicative accessibility.

Additionally, visual schedules are particularly useful for structuring spaces, activities, and professionals involved in the teaching-learning process. Their use promotes routine anticipation (Figure 1), reduces uncertainty, and enhances student autonomy across different school contexts, especially for those needing structure and predictability.

Fig.1

Finally, **social stories** represent a relevant tool for working on anticipation and understanding of everyday situations, special school days, or changes in routine. Through visual and structured narratives, students can more clearly understand expected behaviors and action sequences associated with different social and educational contexts, fostering adaptation to the environment and social competence (Gray, 2010).

5.4. PRACTICAL APPLICATION IN EDUCATIONAL CONTEXTS

Regarding educational contexts, activities are designed to address language components (form, content, and use), as well as executive functions and theory of mind, with the goal of improving communicative skills and promoting active student participation in the school environment.

First, **phonetic-phonological components and metalinguistic skills** (lexical, syllabic, and phonemic awareness) are targeted. This is achieved through the activity "Separamos la palabra" (Figure 2), in which the student identifies the word from an image, separates its sounds with snaps, and divides its syllables with claps. In this way, the development of metalinguistic and suprasegmental skills is supported through gestural aids that facilitate generalization.

Fig.2

Source: Own elaboration

Regarding **morphological components**, activities involving nominal and verbal inflection are conducted to promote their use in communicative contexts. In the task "Unimos las partes" (Figure 3), the student must place the appropriate articles or determiners next to the images, such as "el gato" (the cat) and "la flor" (the flower), thereby working on gender and number agreement.

Fig.3

- INDICA EL DETERMINANTE QUE CORRESPONDE A CADA IMAGEN Y COLOCALO EN LA CASILLA

CATEGORÍA 1

Source: Own elaboration.

For **syntactic structure**, the focus is on constructing statements, their length, and the use of connectors to form coherent sentences. In the activity "Hacemos frases" (Figure 4), the student must choose the correct sentence from two options and reproduce it orally using images representing the sentence elements, facilitating verbal and linguistic comprehension.

Fig.4

• **ELIGE LA OPCIÓN CORRECTA**

The correct options are: "la niña conduce un coche" y "Papa, la niña y el niño ríen". Source: Own elaboration

In the **semantic component**, intervention targets the student's receptive and expressive vocabulary by semantic categories. In the task "Colocamos las familias" (Figure 5), the student places lexical family elements into categories such as fruits, objects, and farm animals. As they place the elements, they reproduce their image-based representation, for example, "manzana" (apple), "gorra" (cap), "gallina" (hen), aiming to improve communicative skills, word category discrimination, and verbal expression.

Fig.5

• COLOCA LAS TARJETAS EN LA CATEGORÍA QUE CORRESPONDE

CATEGORÍA 1

Source: Own elaboration

For **pragmatic components**, functional language use across various contexts is addressed through tasks featuring characters expressing thoughts related to the presented situation (see Figure 6), as in the activity "¿Qué piensan?". In this way, the student places the corresponding speech bubbles next to the images and their related context.

Fig.6

• Coloca los bocadillos al personaje que corresponda.

Source: Own elaboration.

Regarding **executive functions**, exercises are designed to enable the student to plan, order, and sequence actions in an organized and structured manner. For this purpose, the activity "Ordenamos las escenas" (Figure 7) involves placing images of an action sequence in chronological order, supporting visual information processing and functional reasoning.

Finally, **Theory of Mind** is addressed through specific exercises and activities targeting different emotions and emotional states in everyday situations. This type of intervention is essential for fostering understanding of others' thoughts, intentions, desires, and feelings, an area often challenging for students with ASD. Through identifying and recognizing facial expressions, gestures, body postures, and specific social contexts, students progressively learn to interpret how others feel and anticipate possible emotional responses to various events.

Additionally, these activities develop skills related to empathy, social communication, and peer interaction, promoting greater adaptation to diverse school and social environments. Visual supports, images, pictograms, social stories, and guided questions are used to help students reflect on their own and others' emotions. An example is the activity "¿Cómo se sienten?" (Figure 8), where students observe various scenes and match them to basic emotions such as joy, sadness, anger, fear, or surprise, then explain why each character might

feel that way. This promotes not only emotional recognition but also understanding of the causes and consequences of emotional states in different social contexts.

Fig.8

- **¿CÓMO SE SIENTEN ESTAS PERSONAS? RODEA LA EMOCIÓN CORRECTA**

In the exercise, the emotions of joy, anger, and sadness are shown; the student must circle the emotion that each carácter represents

Source: Own elaboration.

5.5. EVALUATION OF THE INTERVENTION

Evaluation of the intervention should be understood as a continuous and systematic process aimed at assessing student progress in the communicative, linguistic, and social skills addressed through the proposed activities. In this sense, evaluation focuses not only on final outcomes but also on the student's evolution during the teaching-learning process and their ability to generalize learning to different educational contexts.

One key technique is **systematic observation**, through which professionals directly record student participation, functional use of communication, social interaction, and responses to various classroom situations. This observation helps identify needs, adjust intervention strategies, and track the evolution of communicative behaviors.

Rubrics are also used to provide structured analysis of aspects related to comprehension, expression, pragmatic language use, executive functions, and theory of mind. These tools objectify performance levels and establish clear, individualized progress indicators.

Communication logs are likewise a valuable instrument for documenting the frequency, intent, and functionality of the student's communicative interactions across contexts and interlocutors. These records facilitate identification of advances in communicative initiative, conversation maintenance, or use of visual supports and augmentative systems.

Finally, evaluation is based on **comparing an initial assessment with progress observed** after intervention implementation. This comparison assesses strategy effectiveness and verifies student evolution in communicative, linguistic, and social competencies, supporting more tailored interventions based on actual needs.

6. DISCUSSION

Following the development of the didactic proposal, the analysis of the profile associated with CHD8 syndrome reveals the presence of neurocognitive, communicative, and behavioral characteristics that require a structured, functional, and tailored educational response.

Despite advances in the clinical characterization of this genetic alteration, there remains a notable scarcity of research focused on its linguistic and communicative development in educational contexts, limiting evidence-based pedagogical decision-making. This situation reinforces the need to design didactic proposals that integrate neurogenetic knowledge with educational practice, offering clear guidance for intervention in communicative and social skills.

In line with the above, the results of the theoretical review highlight the importance of comprehensive approaches that incorporate executive functions and social cognition as fundamental axes of communicative learning. Likewise, the complexity of the profile calls for coordinated, interdisciplinary intervention among teachers, specialists, and healthcare professionals, complemented by support networks ensuring strategy continuity across contexts.

Within this framework, community resources play a key role in awareness-raising and family support. In the Spanish context, the Emuná CHD8 association serves as a reference point, providing specialized information, emotional support, and networking among families and professionals, contributing to greater understanding of the syndromic profile and more contextualized intervention.

Complementarily, the study's findings underscore the relevance of educational interventions that systematically integrate language components (form, content, and use), along with executive functions and theory of mind, fostering active student participation in inclusive settings. However, this need contrasts with the scarcity of specific empirical evidence, making it difficult to validate concrete educational strategies for this profile.

This limited body of research highlights the need to continue deepening the development of more consistent, evidence-based educational intervention models. In this regard, it is particularly important to advance proposals that effectively translate neurogenetic knowledge to the school context, an aspect revisited in the final reflection of this work.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis confirms that the profile associated with mutations in the CHD8 gene has significant implications for students' communicative and linguistic development, as well as school participation. Despite advances in its biomedical characterization, important gaps persist in developing tailored educational responses, particularly regarding pedagogical and communicative strategies in inclusive contexts.

This framework reinforces the importance of implementing structured, functional, and adapted educational interventions to students' neurocognitive and linguistic profiles, integrating language components (form, content, and use) with executive functions and theory of mind. Likewise, the use of visual supports, augmentative systems, and anticipation strategies is established as a key resource for enhancing communicative accessibility, environmental understanding, and active classroom participation.

It is equally important to develop new research lines from educational, speech therapy, and pedagogical perspectives to validate the effectiveness of proposed

interventions and deepen specific knowledge of this profile. Current empirical evidence limitations hinder consolidating data-based intervention models, requiring greater scientific output oriented toward educational practice.

Finally, addressing rare neurogenetic profiles demands an interdisciplinary approach in which teachers, hearing and language specialists, speech therapists, healthcare professionals, and families work coordinately. In this context, community resources like the Emuná CHD8 association play a relevant role in support, awareness, and coordination across settings, contributing to more inclusive, coherent educational responses tailored to students' real needs.

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